

PECULIARITIES OF DISPERSION LAWS OF A HIGHLY EXCITED THREE-LEVEL ATOM WITH AN EQUIDISTANT ENERGY SPECTRUM

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Abstract

A dispersion law for the system of three-level atoms with an equidistant energy spectrum interacting with resonant laser radiation has been obtained taking into account two successive optically allowed one-photon transitions and an optically allowed two-photon transition between the lower and upper levels. It has been shown that the dispersion law consists of three polariton branches. The effects of repulsion and attraction of branches of the dispersion law and their intersection, as well as the self-consistent variation of the photon–atom coupling constant, have been predicted.

1. Introduction

Increased attention is currently focused on the study of processes of the interaction of laser radiation with matter in low-dimensional media. Bose–Einstein condensation and superfluidity in exciton–polariton systems in microcavities were studied in [1–5]. Studies of phenomena caused by the strong coupling of photons to atomic systems are of particular interest. Nonlinear optical phenomena in three- and multilevel atomic systems were studied taking into account optically induced one-photon transitions between successive pairs of neighboring levels [6–10]. At the same time, direct two-photon transitions between the first and third levels are optically allowed in three-level atomic systems. In terms of this model, a number of active levels, e.g., three levels, which are in resonance with the incident laser radiation, are “cut” from the system. Optically induced one-photon transitions from the ground state of a crystal to an exciton state and from the exciton state to a biexciton state, as well as a direct two-photon transition from the ground state of the crystal to the biexciton level, occur in the exciton region of the spectrum. In CdS and CdSe semiconductors, where the binding energy of a biexciton is vanishingly low, this model of matter is in essence an equidistant three-level model. Equidistant multilevel systems are commonly used in the theory of cascade lasers [11, 12]. It is noteworthy that the model of quantum oscillator is also equidistant. To the best of our knowledge, one-photon and two-photon transitions in the dynamics of three-level atoms have not been taken into account simultaneously.

2. Formulation of the Problem: Dispersion Relation

Below, studies of the dispersion law of three-level atoms with an equidistant energy spectrum interacting with photons of an ultrashort pulse of resonant laser radiation are reported. States 1 and 3 (Fig. 1) have the same parity; therefore, a one-photon transition between them is optically forbidden. However, a direct two-photon transition between these levels is optically allowed. For this reason, we take into account one photon transitions between levels $1 \rightleftharpoons 2$ and $2 \rightleftharpoons 3$ and two-photon transitions induced by photons of a single pulse between levels 1 and 3 (Fig. 1). Although the used scheme of an equidistant energy spectrum seems specific, the Λ , V , and Σ models of three-level atoms are widely used in atomic optics [10]. The Hamiltonian of the interaction of an atom with photons can be written in the form

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{1}{\hbar} \hat{H}_{int} = & -g_{12} \hat{a}_1 \hat{c} \hat{a}_2^+ - g_{12}^* \hat{a}_2 \hat{c}^+ \hat{a}_1^+ - g_{23} \hat{a}_2 \hat{c} \hat{a}_3^+ - g_{23}^* \hat{a}_3 \hat{c}^+ \hat{a}_2^+ - \\ & -g_{13} \hat{a}_1 \hat{c} \hat{c} \hat{a}_3^+ - g_{13}^* \hat{a}_3 \hat{c}^+ \hat{c}^+ \hat{a}_1^+, \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

where $\hat{a}_j (j = 1, 2, 3)$ is the annihilation operator of the atom at the j th level, \hat{c} is the photon operator with frequency ω_c , and g_{ij} are the constants of single photon conversion of the atom from the i th level to the j th level. The eigenfrequencies of atoms at levels 2 and 3 are ω_0 and $2\omega_0$, respectively (Fig. 1). Successive one-photon transitions between levels $1 \rightleftharpoons 2$ and $2 \rightleftharpoons 3$ are considered as optically allowed. At the same time, a two-photon transition between levels $2 \rightleftharpoons 3$ is also optically allowed under the action of photons of the same pulse, which is described by the last two terms in Eq. (1).

In addition, we assumed that the half-width of the incident pulse is smaller than the relaxation time of atoms. In this case, relaxation processes can be neglected because the time of action of the pulse is insufficient for their development.

Fig. 1. Scheme of the equidistant energy spectrum of the three-level atom interacting with photons with frequency ω_c .

Using Eq. (1), one can obtain equations of motion for operators \hat{a}_j and \hat{c} ; the averaging of these equations in the mean field approximation gives the system of nonlinear evolution equations for amplitudes $a_j = \langle \hat{a}_j \rangle (j = 1, 2, 3)$ and $c = \langle \hat{c} \rangle$:

$$\begin{cases} i\dot{a}_1 = -g_{12}^* c^* a_2 - g_{13}^* c^* c^* a_3, \\ i\dot{a}_2 = \omega_0 a_2 - g_{12} a_1 c - g_{23}^* c^* a_3, \\ i\dot{a}_3 = 2\omega_0 a_3 - g_{23} a_2 c - g_{13} a_1 c c, \\ i\dot{c} = \omega_c c - g_{12}^* a_1^* a_2 - g_{23}^* a_2^* a_3 - 2g_{13}^* a_1^* c^* a_3. \end{cases} \quad (2)$$

We now derive a dispersion relation for the system near frequency ω_0 of the second atomic level. According to the equation for \dot{a}_2 , the rate of variation in amplitude a_2 is determined by $a_1 c$ and $c^* a_3$. The term with $(a_1 c)$ describes the contribution to the rate of variation in amplitude a_2 owing to the disappearance of the atom at the first level and the disappearance of a photon with frequency ω_c with the transition of the atom to level 2. The term with $(c^* a_3)$ describes the process of disappearance of the atom at level 3 with the creation of a photon at frequency ω_2 with the transition of the atom to level 2. The respective operators $\hat{c}\hat{a}_1$ and $\hat{c}^*\hat{a}_3$ describe states with energies $\hbar\omega_c$ and $\hbar(2\omega_0 - \omega_c)$, which are equal to energy ω_0 of the second atomic level. Consequently, the state of the atom at level 2 and the replica of excited state 3 shifted below by photon energy ω_c are degenerate in energy.

Below, we assume that amplitude c is much larger than the amplitudes of atoms at the respective levels ($c \gg a_1, a_2, a_3$). We refer to this approximation as the given photon density approximation. In this approximation, the second, third, and fourth terms in the last equation in Eqs. (2) are vanishingly small and can be neglected. In this case, the solution of this equation has a simple form: $c = c_0 e^{-i\omega_c t}$, where c_0 is the initial amplitude of photons. Accordingly, it is evident that the envelope of function $c(t)$ in the given photon density approximation does not vary with time: $|c|^2 = c_0^2 \equiv f_0 = const$. Then, the equation for a_2 in Eqs. (2) and the equations for $a_1 c$ and $c^* a_3$ in the given photon density approximation form a closed system of three equations for the amplitudes of quasiparticles with the same quasi-energy $\hbar\omega_0 \approx \hbar\omega_c \approx \hbar(\Omega_0 - \omega_c)$:

$$\begin{aligned} i\dot{a}_2 &= \omega_0 a_2 - g_{12}(a_1 c) - g_{23}^*(c^* a_3), \\ i(a_1 c)^{\bullet} &= \omega_c(a_1 c) - g_{12}^* f_0 a_2 - g_{13}^* f_0(c^* a_3), \\ i(c^* a_3)^{\bullet} &= (\Omega_0 - \omega_c)(c^* a_3) - g_{23} f_0 a_2 - g_{13} f_0(a_1 c), \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

where f_0 is the (given) photon density. Thus, in the given photon density approximation, the derived system of Eqs. (3) for functions $a_2, a_1 c$ and $c^* a_3$ is linear. We seek a solution in the form $a_2, a_1 c, c^* a_3 \sim e^{-i\omega t}$, where ω is the desired eigenfrequency of atomic polaritons. Then, we obtain a system of three linear algebraic equations for the steady-state amplitudes; the determinant of this system specifies the dispersion law of atomic polaritons in the form

$$\begin{aligned} (\omega - \omega_0)(\omega - \omega_c)(\omega - 2\omega_0 + \omega_c) - \Omega_{12}^2(\omega - 2\omega_0 + \omega_c) - \Omega_{23}^2(\omega - \omega_c) - \\ - \Omega_{13}^2(\omega - \omega_0) + 2\Omega_{12}\Omega_{23}\Omega_{13} \cos \vartheta = 0, \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

where $\Omega_{12}^2 = g_{12}^2 f_0$, $\Omega_{23}^2 = g_{23}^2 f_0$ and $\Omega_{13}^2 = g_{13}^2 f_0^2$ are the respective Rabi frequencies and ϑ is the phase difference between the coupling constants. It is evident that the squared Rabi frequency Ω_{12}^2 of the optically allowed one-photon transition between the first and second levels is proportional both to squared transition matrix element g_{12}^2 and to photon density f_0 . The squared Rabi frequency Ω_{23}^2 of the optically allowed one-photon transition between levels 2 and 3 is proportional to the square of the matrix element of transition dipole moment g_{23}^2 and the photon density. Finally, the squared Rabi frequency Ω_{13}^2 is proportional to the matrix element squared g_{13}^2 of the optically allowed two-photon transition between levels 1 and 3 and the squared photon density. The dispersion relation given by Eq. (4) includes six frequency parameters ($\omega, \omega_0, \omega_c, \Omega_{12}, \Omega_{23}, \Omega_{13}$) and phase difference ϑ . Below, frequencies $\omega, \omega_0, \omega_c, \Omega_{23}$ and Ω_{13} are normalized to the lowest Rabi frequency Ω_{12} . In most semiconductors, frequencies ω, ω_0 , and ω_c are about 10^{15} s^{-1} , whereas Rabi frequencies Ω_{12}, Ω_{23} and Ω_{13} are two or three orders of magnitude lower. In addition, it is generally clear that the Rabi frequencies are approximately identical at moderate excitation levels and frequency Ω_{13} at low (high) levels is lower (higher) than frequencies Ω_{12} and Ω_{23} . With an increase in the photon density, Rabi frequency Ω_{13} increases more rapidly than frequencies Ω_{12} and Ω_{23} .

According to Eq. (4), the dispersion law for frequency ω of atomic polariton waves has three real roots, which form three dispersion branches depending on frequency $\omega_c = ck_c$ of incident photons, where k_c is the wavenumber. The shape and location of branches significantly depend on photon density f_0 . Equations (4) include three terms, each proportional to the respective squared Rabi frequency or to the square of the absolute value of the respective transition matrix element. These three terms describe independent contributions from the respective processes to the dispersion law. The sign of the corresponding coupling constant with respect to two other signs in the Hamiltonian given by Eq. (1) is of no significance. The last term in Eq. (4) is proportional to the product of three different Rabi frequencies (or three coupling constants g_{12}, g_{23} and g_{13}). This term is due to the joint action (quantum interference) of all three processes. If at least one coupling constant is zero, then this term is absent. In this case, it is very important to take into account the signs of the coupling constants or, more precisely, phase relations between them because the dispersion law depends also on phase difference ϑ between these constants. The last term in Eq. (4) is due to the coherence of the interaction of photons with atoms. Hence, the experimental establishment of the features of the dispersion law with the simultaneous inclusion of all three optical transitions can promote determining the phase relations between the coupling constants.

3. Dispersion Law of the Three-Level Atom with the Equidistant Energy Spectrum

We now consider the features of the dispersion law for the three-level atom with the equidistant energy spectrum in more detail. The eigenfrequencies of the second and third (excited) levels are ω_0 and $2\omega_0$, respectively. Photons of a single pulse with frequency ω_c are incident on the atom. It is evident that, at $\Omega_{13} = 0$ and $\Omega_{23} = 0$ (limit of two-level atom), Eq. (4) is split into two equations, namely, $(\omega - \omega_0)(\omega - \omega_c) - \Omega_{12}^2 = 0$ and $\omega - 2\omega_0 + \omega_c = 0$. The former equation is the well-known polariton equation, while the latter equation is the dispersion ratio for “bare” photons that do not interact with the medium. Both polariton-like branches of the dispersion law intersect the straight line $\omega - 2\omega_0 + \omega_c = 0$ at two points $C(\omega - \Omega_{12}/\sqrt{2}, \omega + \Omega_{12}/\sqrt{2})$ and $D(\omega + \Omega_{12}/\sqrt{2}, \omega - \Omega_{12}/\sqrt{2})$ (Fig. 2a).

If, e.g., $\Omega_{23} \neq 0$ but $\Omega_{13} = 0$, i.e., if the photon interacts with the atom through the $2 \leftrightarrow 3$ transition, Eq. (4) is not split into two independent equations. In view of the interaction, the branches of the dispersion law intersect at the points of energy degeneracy C and D . As a result, the dispersion law is split into three separate branches, namely, upper, middle, and lower. The upper and middle branches have extrema near point C , whereas the middle and lower branches have extrema near point D . With an increase in Ω_{23} , splitting increase and the positions of the extrema are shifted. In terms of the dimensionless frequencies

$$\Delta = \frac{\omega - \omega_0}{\Omega_{12}}, \quad \delta = \frac{\omega_c - \omega_0}{\Omega_{12}}, \quad \omega_{23} = \frac{\Omega_{23}}{\Omega_{12}}, \quad \omega_{13} = \frac{\Omega_{13}}{\Omega_{12}}. \quad (5)$$

dispersion relation (4) is represented in the form

$$\Delta^3 - \Delta(1 + \delta^2 + \omega_{23}^2 + \omega_{13}^2) + \delta(\omega_{23}^2 - 1) + 2\omega_{23}\omega_{13} \cos \vartheta = 0. \quad (6)$$

According to Eq. (6), the dispersion law $\Delta(\delta)$ consists of three branches having both ascending and descending sections of the $\Delta(\delta)$ dependence. In the general case, the solutions of Eq. (6) are given by the formulas

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta_1 &= (2/\sqrt{3})\sqrt{1 + \delta^2 + \omega_{23}^2 + \omega_{13}^2} \cos \frac{\alpha}{3}, \\ \Delta_{2,3} &= -(2/\sqrt{3})\sqrt{1 + \delta^2 + \omega_{23}^2 + \omega_{13}^2} \cos \frac{\alpha \pm \pi}{3}, \end{aligned} \quad (7)$$

where

$$\cos \alpha = \frac{(\omega_{23}^2 - 1)\delta + 2\omega_{23}\omega_{13} \cos \vartheta}{(2/3\sqrt{3})(1 + \delta^2 + \omega_{23}^2 + \omega_{13}^2)^{3/2}}. \quad (8)$$

Fig. 2. Dispersion laws of $\Delta = \frac{\omega - \omega_0}{\Omega_{12}}$ versus $\delta = \frac{\omega_c - \omega_0}{\Omega_{12}}$ at $\Omega_{23} =$ (a) 0 and (b) 0.5; $\Omega_{13} =$ (solid lines) 0, (dashed lines) 0.5, (dotted lines) 1, and (dash-dotted lines) 1.5; and phase difference $\vartheta = \pi/2$.

We consider $\vartheta = \frac{\pi}{2}$ (Fig. 2). It is evident from Fig. 2a that, at $\omega_{13} \neq 0$ and $\omega_{23} \neq 0$, points C and D are split and three separate branches of the dispersion law, which are characterized by the presence of ascending and descending sections of the $\Delta(\delta)$ dependence, appear. The distances between the branches of the dispersion law increase with ω_{13} (Figs. 2a, 2b). The minima on the upper branch are gradually shifted toward shorter wavelengths, whereas the maxima on the lower branch are shifted toward longer wavelengths, and the middle branch slowly changes its profile with an increase in δ remaining near the straight line $\Delta=0$. At $\omega_{23} = \omega_{13}$, the upper and lower branches become symmetric with respect to both $\Delta=0$ and $\delta=0$, and the middle branch is on the straight line $\Delta=0$ at any ω_{13} values. Accordingly, the coordinates of the upper and lower polariton branches are given by the formulas $\Delta = \pm\sqrt{1 + \delta^2 + \omega_{23}^2 + \omega_{13}^2}$. Thus, the eigenfrequencies of the lower and upper polariton branches increase with $|\delta|$. The shift of the lower and upper polariton branches continues at high ω_{23} values. Furthermore, the behavior of the middle branch becomes more distinct and its variation along the Δ axis increases significantly. It is remarkable that the middle branch of the dispersion law lies on the straight line $\Delta=0$ (i.e., it does not change under a variation in δ) at the parameter $\omega_{23} = 1$ and any ω_{13} values. Thus, according to Fig. 2, the shapes and positions of the branches of the dispersion law of atomic polaritons significantly depend on Rabi frequencies Ω_{12} , Ω_{23} , and Ω_{13} .

We now discuss the behavior of the branches of the dispersion law for the case $\vartheta = 0$ (Fig. 3). Plots $\Delta(\delta)$ at $\vartheta = \frac{\pi}{2}$ and $\vartheta = 0$ in Fig. 3a coincide with Fig. 2a at $\omega_{23} = 0$, because the term with $\cos\vartheta$ vanishes at $\omega_{23} = 1$. Differences in the behavior of the branches of the dispersion law appear only when all Rabi frequencies are nonzero, i.e., when the term with $\cos\vartheta$ is nonzero. It is evident from Eq. (6) that the middle branch of the dispersion law coincides with the straight line $\Delta=0$ at $\omega_{23} = 1$ and $\omega_{13} = 1$. Significant differences are seen in Figs. 2b and 3. Figure 2b shows the increasing repulsion between the middle and upper branches of the dispersion law with an increase in ω_{13} at the fixed value of $\omega_{23} = 0.5$. At the same time, in Fig. 3, this process is slower; with an increase in ω_{13} , the branches of the dispersion law are located in a certain region bounded by the middle and lower branches (solid lines). With an increase in ω_{13} , the middle and upper branches first attract each other and then repulsion between them appears, whereas the lower and middle branches only repel each other. At $\omega_{13} = 0$, the upper and lower polariton branches are symmetric with respect to the middle branch.

Asymmetry appears with an increase in ω_{13} , when the middle and upper branches first approach each other with increasing ω_{13} and then begin to deviate from each other. Moreover, the upper and middle branches of the dispersion law intersect each other at $\omega_{13} = \omega_{23} = 1$ and, then, again deviate from each other. Thus, the upper and middle branches spectrally approach each other with increasing ω_{13} , intersect each other at $\omega_{13} = \omega_{23} = 1$ (dotted lines), and then deviate from each other (Fig. 3).

It is evident from Fig. 3 that the lower and middle branches of the dispersion law strongly deviate from each other. This feature of the branches of the dispersion law can be interpreted as a change in the photon–atom coupling constant. Thus, the renormalization of the energy spectrum of polaritons is clearly manifested in strong coupling in the long-wavelength region from frequency ω_0 and in weakening of the coupling in the short-wavelength region. This fact also indicates the displacement of the actual points of the k -space. It can be stated that an increase in

the pump intensity in experiments will lead to a change in the coupling strength and to the spectral displacement of the actual points in the k -space.

Fig. 3. Dispersion laws of $\Delta = \frac{\omega - \omega_0}{\Omega_{12}}$ versus $\delta = \frac{\omega_c - \omega_0}{\Omega_{12}}$ at $\Omega_{23}=0.5$, Ω_{13} = (solid lines) 0, (dashed lines) 0.5, (dotted lines) 1, and (dash-dotted lines) 1.5; and phase difference $\vartheta = 0$.

Fig. 4. Dispersion laws of $\Delta = \frac{\omega - \omega_0}{\Omega_{12}}$ versus $\delta = \frac{\omega_c - \omega_0}{\Omega_{12}}$ at $\Omega_{23}=0.5$, Ω_{13} (solid lines) 0, (dashed lines) 0.5, (dotted lines) 1, and (dash-dotted lines) 1.5; and phase difference $\vartheta = \pi$.

The results shown in Fig. 4 for $\vartheta = \pi$ are similar to those shown in Fig. 3 for $\vartheta = 0$ (after the substitution of $-\Delta$ and $-\delta$ for Δ and δ , respectively). It is evident that the main features, namely, spectral approach, intersection, and subsequent deviation, appear now between the lower and middle branches of the dispersion law.

The eigenfrequencies of the three branches of polaritons significantly depend on the level of excitation of the atomic system. They determine nutation frequencies $\tilde{\Omega}_{12}$, $\tilde{\Omega}_{23}$, and $\tilde{\Omega}_{13}$ (new Rabi frequencies) of polaritons, which are the differences of the eigenfrequencies of polaritons. If the frequencies of two polaritons, e.g., the upper and middle polaritons, coincide with each other, the respective nutation frequency is zero. In this case, the process of nutation is not due to beating of the three polariton branches; it includes nutation oscillations at a single frequency.

4. Conclusions

To summarize, the dispersion law of atomic polaritons has been studied for three-level atoms with the equidistant energy spectrum that interact with intense resonant laser radiation. It has been shown that the dispersion law of atomic polaritons consists of three branches whose position and shape are determined by the Rabi frequencies of optically allowed one-photon transitions between levels $1 \leftrightarrow 2$ and $2 \leftrightarrow 3$ and an optically allowed two-photon transition between levels $1 \leftrightarrow 3$. The repulsion and attraction of the branches of the dispersion law, their intersection, self-consistent variation of the coupling strength of photons with atoms, and a significant dependence on the phase difference between the coupling constants are predicted.

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